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October 2024

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Maryse Guinebretiere for peer-reviewing and giving valuable feedback, Marine Lacampagne for her work during the initial pilot study, and Dines, Catie, Amélie, Chloë, Eve, and Perrine for their assistance with data collection. We are grateful to the producers who welcomed us onto their farms.

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This review is a publication of the European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare for Poultry and small farmed animals. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA was designated by the European Union on 4 October 2019 through Regulation (EU) 2019/1685, in accordance with Articles 95 and 96 of Regulation (EU) 2017/625. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This review can be downloaded for free at [[10.5281/zenodo.14008430](https://zenodo.org/record/14008430)]

Citation: Riber, A.B., Rasmussen, S.N., & Wurtz, K.E. (2024). Latency-to-lie test without water is a valid objective method for on-farm assessment of walking ability of broilers. 10.5281/zenodo.14008430. [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14008430>]

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1 Executive Summary

The Latency-to-Lie (LTL) test is an objective method used to assess the walking ability of broilers. Traditionally, the test involved placing birds in shallow water to measure how long they would stand before sitting, with sitting earlier indicating poorer mobility. This study aimed to evaluate the validity of modified versions of the LTL test without using water, making it more suitable for on-farm use. We tested the performance of the LTL test with and without a box to contain the birds using two different broiler hybrids, Ross 308 ($n = 159$) and Rustic Gold ($n = 186$). Following gait scoring using the Bristol scale, the birds were placed in a standing position in a clear plastic box lined with litter for the first LTL test, with a maximum test duration of 300 s. After completion of the test and a 120 s period of rest, the birds were tested again without a box by placing them on the litter near flockmates. Latencies to lie were negatively correlated with gait scores (with box: $\rho = -0.44$, $P < 0.001$; without box: $\rho = -0.46$, $P < 0.001$), with longer standing times indicating better mobility. Within each gait score category, there was no effect of hybrid on latencies to lie for either of the tests. Using a box provided better differentiation between gait scores compared to the test without a box. The results suggest that the LTL test without water, especially with the use of a box, is a valid method for assessing walking ability of broilers on commercial farms, differing in hybrids and production systems. Thus, the LTL test without water provides an objective, robust and practical alternative to traditional gait scoring methods.

2 Introduction

Poor walking ability in broilers is a significant issue for both their welfare and the productivity. Birds with impaired mobility may face challenges in accessing food and water (Butterworth et al., 2002; Weeks et al., 2000), which can lead to slower growth rates and lower body weight at slaughter (Gocsik et al., 2014). In addition, poor walking ability can prevent broilers from engaging in normal behaviours, such as dustbathing, foraging, and preening (Vestergaard & Sanotra, 1999; Weeks et al., 2002). The increased level of inactivity adds to the risk of developing contact dermatitis if litter quality is poor (Robins & Phillips, 2011). Poor walking ability may be associated with pain (Caplen et al., 2013; Danbury et al., 2000; Hothersall et al., 2016; McGeown et al., 1999; Riber et al., 2021), increased mortality (Wideman Jr et al., 2012) and a higher risk of condemnations at slaughter (Granquist et al., 2019).

The most commonly used method to assess the walking ability of broilers is the Bristol scale – a 6-point gait scoring system developed by Kestin et al. (1992). In this scoring protocol, broilers are visually assessed while walking and assigned a score ranging from 0, indicating no detectable mobility issues, to 5, where the bird is unable to walk. The Bristol scale is often used as the gold standard in the validation of alternative assessment methods. While this method is widely accepted, it has its limitations. It requires dedicated training and regular calibration, can be subjective, and is time-consuming when assessing large flocks.

To address these limitations, the Latency-to-Lie (LTL) test has been developed as a more objective alternative. The LTL test measures how long a bird remains standing before sitting down, with longer durations being associated with better walking ability. In the traditional version of this test, birds are placed in a tub of shallow water, which discourages them from sitting (Berg & Sanotra, 2003; Groves & Muir, 2014; Santos et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2017; Weeks et al., 2002; Weimer et al., 2020). It is assumed that birds find sitting in water to be aversive and thus the presence of water would encourage them to stay standing for as long as possible. However, the use of water of a constant temperature is impractical on farms. Later studies have used modified LTL tests which omitted the use of water (Bailie et al., 2013; Bailie & O’Connell, 2014; Baxter et al., 2021; Norring et al., 2019), but these studies made no direct comparisons between latencies to lie and gait scores, i.e., the LTL tests without water have not been validated. This study aimed to validate the use of LTL tests without water, both the version with and the version without a box to contain the broilers. A sub aim was to assess the performance of the two versions of the LTL test without water on different broiler hybrids.

3 Materials and methods

3.1. Animals and housing

The study was conducted on two commercial broiler farms, each visited twice, in Denmark in May and July 2023. A total of 159 Ross 308 broilers (flock 1: 58, flock 2: 101) and 186 Rustic Gold broilers (flock 1: 84, flock 2: 102) were assessed a few days before slaughter. The birds were

housed in mixed-sex groups under conventional farming conditions, with Ross 308 broilers (growth rate: 62-63 g/day) at a stocking density of 40 kg/m² and Rustic Gold broilers (growth rate: 50-51 g/day) housed at a stocking density of 38 kg/m². The target slaughter weight was 2.3 kg for both hybrids.

3.2. Data collection

Birds were first gait scored by a single trained observer using the six-point Bristol scale where scores range from 0 (no detectable abnormality) to 5 (unable to walk) (Kestin et al., 1992). Birds were selected nonrandomly leading to overall counts of 29, 84, 183, 36, 13, and 0 birds with gait scores 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 respectively. Birds with a gait score of 5 were excluded from this study due to welfare concerns and their inability to stand, which disqualifies them from the LTL test criteria.

After being gait scored, the birds were then individually placed in a standing position in a clear plastic box (smart store™, 59 x 39 x 43 cm) lined with litter from the floor of the broiler house. The timekeeper measured the time it took for each bird to sit down (i.e., first contact of the hocks and breast with the litter), with a maximum test duration of 300 s. After a rest period of 120 s, the LTL test was repeated without the use of a box, with the bird placed on the ground in a standing position near a group of flockmates. The duration of the rest period was determined according to the length of typical daytime resting bouts found in broilers of similar body weight (Forslind et al., 2021; 2022).

Figure 1: LTL test using a box. The test has come to an end, as the broiler is sitting down, having its resting period before the LTL test without a box. Source: ANIVET

3.3. Statistical analyses

Statistical analyses were performed using R Statistical Software v4.3.3 (R Core Team, 2024). Spearman’s rank correlation coefficients were calculated to examine the relationship between gait scores and latencies to lie (s) for both LTL tests (i.e., with and without a box). To determine if latencies to lie differed between tests using or not using a box, a Friedman test was employed. For assessing significant differences in latencies to lie between gait scores, a Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum test was conducted. To investigate differences between each pair of gait scores, post hoc pairwise Dunn’s tests were performed, with a Benjamini-Hochberg correction applied for multiple comparisons. Additionally, a Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum test was used within each gait score to evaluate the impact of hybrid on latencies to lie. The number of birds remaining standing for the maximum duration of 300 s was low (with box: n = 7; without box: n = 5) and data on these birds were therefore included in the analyses.

4 Results

Table 1 shows the number of birds within each genotype and gait score category per flock which were included in the study.

Table 1: Number of broilers within genotype (Ross 308 and Rustic Gold) and gait score category (0, 1, 2, 3, 4) which were tested during visits (two per genotype).

Genotype	Flock	Gait Score				
		0	1	2	3	4
Ross 308	1	4	11	30	8	5
	2	14	24	54	6	3
	Total	18	35	84	14	8
Rustic Gold	1	4	22	45	12	1
	2	7	27	54	10	4
	Total	11	49	99	22	5
All	Total	29	84	183	36	13

4.1. Validity with and without the use of a box

The results showed a strong negative correlation between latencies to lie and gait scores (with box: $\rho = -0.44$, $P < 0.001$; without box: $\rho = -0.46$, $P < 0.001$). Birds with lower gait scores (indicating better mobility) remained standing for longer periods, while birds with higher gait scores (indicating worse mobility) sat down more quickly (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The proportion of birds remaining standing across the test duration (300 s) when the test was conducted with (A) and without (B) a box.

Latencies to lie were lower when the test was conducted without the box, compared to with the box ($\chi^2 = 127.25$, $df = 1$, $P < 0.001$; Figure 3). Significant differences in latencies to lie were observed between the different gait scores (with box: $\chi^2 = 75.35$, $df = 4$, $P < 0.001$; without box: $\chi^2 = 75.00$, $df = 4$, $P < 0.001$). Post hoc pairwise tests showed that latencies to lie while using a box were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) for all pairs of gait scores, except for the comparison between scores 0 and 1 ($P = 0.17$). When not using a box, significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in latencies to lie were found for all pairs of gait scores except for the comparisons between 2 and 3 (tendency, $P = 0.08$), and 3 and 4 ($P = 0.11$).

Figure 3: Latencies to lie (s) by gait score (0 to 4) when conducting the LTL test with a box (A) and without a box (B).

4.2. Validity of the test for assessing two hybrids

Within each gait score category, there were no differences in latencies to lie between the two hybrids, except for gait score 1 when conducting the test without a box where the Ross 308 hybrid tended to have longer latencies to lie than the Rustic Gold hybrid ($P = 0.09$; Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4: The proportion of birds remaining standing across the test duration (300 s) when the test was done with (A) and without (B) a box for each hybrid, Ross 308 (red) and Rustic Gold (blue).

Figure 5: Latencies to lie (s) by gait score (0 to 4) for the Ross 308 (red) and Rustic Gold (blue) hybrids when conducting the LTL test with a box (A) and without a box (B).

5 Discussion

Our findings of the LTL tests without water are in line with previous studies on LTL tests using water. For example, Berg & Sanotra (2003) and Weeks et al. (2002) also found clear negative correlations between latencies to lie and gait scores. However, the LTL tests without water used in the current study offer several practical advantages. First, the LTL tests without water are more feasible to conduct on commercial farms. Second, the latencies to lie were shorter without water (e.g., roughly half of those reported by Berg and Sanotra (2003)), which reduces the overall time needed to conduct the tests. In addition, our results suggest that the LTL test, both with and without the box, is suitable for use with different broiler hybrids and different production systems,

which is in line with previous findings of LTL tests conducted with water (Berg & Sanotra, 2003; Weeks et al., 2002).

Interestingly, the use of a box increased the time birds stayed standing compared to not using a box. Other studies, such as Norring et al. (2019) and Bailie et al. (2013), have also reported shorter latencies to lie in tests conducted without water and without a box compared to studies using water in a tub, such as done by Berg and Sanotra (2003). This could be due to the box being a novel environment that made the birds more alert and hesitant to sit down, a position that makes them more vulnerable. Furthermore, birds tested without a box were placed closer to other birds, which may have made them feel more comfortable and led to shorter latencies to lie. It is also worth noting that the test conducted without a box was performed after the birds had already been gait scored and tested with the box. Although the resting period was included to minimize fatigue, it is possible that the birds were more tired during the second test, which could have influenced the results.

Overall, the study demonstrates that the LTL test without water, particularly when using a box, is a valid, objective and practical method for assessing the walking ability of broiler chickens. This method has several advantages: it requires minimal observer training, is quick to conduct, requires no or minimal equipment, and allows a single observer to score multiple birds simultaneously when using boxes. Additionally, LTL tests prevent the need to force birds potentially in pain to walk, unlike most other assessment methods.

Further research is needed to determine the optimal number of birds that should be tested to represent the overall flock. Until a formal assessment is made, we anticipate that the sample size found in current protocols for gait scoring, i.e. 100-150, will be appropriate.

6 Conclusions

The LTL tests without water can serve as a valid objective method for assessing the walking ability of broilers on farm. The LTL test with a box provided slightly better discrimination between birds with different gait scores than the test without a box, suggesting that it may be more accurate for detecting subtle differences in walking ability. The LTL tests without water offer several advantages, including ease of use, minimal equipment requirements, and the ability to be conducted by observers without training. Future studies should explore the sample size needed to ensure representative results of a flock.

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